

University of Galway Submission to the Consultation on Developing a Hydrogen Strategy for Ireland

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Executive Summary

The University of Galway, formerly known as NUI Galway, is a leader in hydrogen research in Ireland and Europe. We wholeheartedly welcome the development of a national strategy for hydrogen. As a latecomer, Ireland has a considerable advantage in that it can learn from the positive and negative aspects of earlier strategies launched by our European neighbours. Now is the time to act decisively and develop a hydrogen strategy that realises Ireland's enormous capacity to produce hydrogen, supports the use of hydrogen to decarbonise hard to abate sectors alongside electrification, gives certainty to project investors and developers, strengthens the hydrogen research sector in Ireland, enables international trade through harmonisation of standards and certification, and promotes the growth of hydrogen valleys to catalyse the deployment of hydrogen across the island.

Specific key recommendations include: (1) The strategy must be part of a renewed focus on national energy diversity and resilience; (2) Public funding for hydrogen research should be increased and should include the establishment of an interdisciplinary national hydrogen centre of excellence; (3) The drafting of a national hydrogen roadmap to determine coherent direction for hydrogen deployment; (4) Sustainability criteria should be imposed on both electricity and hydrogen and the end user should be left to determine the best route to decarbonise their energy/fuel use; (5) Hydrogen supply can be re-risked by mandating low-carbon hydrogen production targets, creating stable, reliable demand for hydrogen in hard-to-abate sectors, providing green hydrogen price support, having clearly defined positions on safety and certifications, and streamlining the planning process for infrastructure; (6) The case for blending hydrogen into the gas grid should be carefully examined and compared to repurposed/new 100% hydrogen pipelines from production sites to a limited number of large users; (7) Geological hydrogen storage should be explored and developed, and policy should ensure viable business cases exist for large-scale hydrogen storage; (8) Hydrogen export should be supported in parallel to domestic demand as it will drive economies of scale and lower unit costs; (9) Communication with the public on the opportunities and risks presented by hydrogen is essential. This should include be meaningful two-way engagement with communities; (10) For hydrogen to have long-term potential to grow, mature and offer the full range of their potential, a strong and unambiguous institutional champion is probably essential.

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Introduction

The University of Galway, formerly known as NUI Galway, is a recognised leader in hydrogen research in Ireland and Europe. University of Galway researchers have leading roles in the major hydrogen research and deployment projects listed below. The university is also a founder-partner in the [Galway Hydrogen Hub](#) (GH2), an initiative to build a multi-modal green hydrogen transport hub in the West of Ireland by 2024. University of Galway research has for the last two years supported the Northern Ireland Department for the Economy in understanding the opportunities and impacts of hydrogen in the energy transition⁶. The university is also a founder-member of [Hydrogen Ireland](#), the association for the hydrogen industry in Ireland.

- [GenComm](#), a 6-year, €11M EU Interreg project to demonstrate the feasibility of hydrogen from curtailed renewable energy in energy-remote communities and in public transport networks.
- [HyLIGHT](#), a 3-year €1.6M project jointly funded by Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) and a 25-strong industry consortium through MaREI, the SFI Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine Research. Its objective is to design a roadmap to widespread green hydrogen deployment in Ireland.
- [SEAFUEL](#), a 5-year €3.6M EU Interreg project to demonstrate the viability of producing zero-emission fuels for transport using abundant resources in islands of the Atlantic.
- [HUGE](#), a 3-year €1.4M EU Interreg project focusing on providing communities with energy security and facilitating the uptake of hydrogen technologies.
- [Green Hysland](#), a 5-year €20.4M project funded by the Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Joint Undertaking aiming at the deployment of a hydrogen ecosystem in the island of Mallorca, Spain.
- [ANEMEL](#), a 4-year €5M project with funding from the European Innovation Council, UK Research and Innovation and the State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation (Switzerland); its objective is the demonstration of a proof-of-concept electrolyser run/operating using low grade water.

Additionally, the University of Galway hosts several ground-breaking projects focused on hydrogen training and novel technologies for the production of hydrogen and other clean fuels. These include [Solar2Chem](#), [Flowphotochem](#), [Nefertiti](#), and [Greenskills4h2](#). Solar2Chem, a 3-year € 4M MSCA-ITN project, has a specific work package on how national hydrogen strategies and policy practices have been explored within the EU hydrogen economy.

Several countries, especially in the EU, have developed national hydrogen strategies in the past two years. Hydrogen production targets and pathways, and demand priorities are summarised in an IEA Bioenergy report on renewable gases, led by University of Galway researchers⁷. We note that Ireland's development of a national hydrogen strategy is comparatively late compared to other European

⁶ Cian Moran, Jochelle Laguipo, Tim Williamson, Josh Williamson, James Carton, Ian Williamson, Rory F.D. Monaghan (2020) Hydrogen - exploring opportunities in the Northern Ireland energy transition. <https://www.nweurope.eu/media/13425/hydrogen-exploring-opportunities-in-the-northern-ireland-energy-transition-march-2021.pdf>

⁷ Fabio Bozzolo Lueckel, Mawini Chanika, Stefan Majer, Uwe Fritsche, Hans Werner Gress, Caoimhe Boyce, Rory Monaghan (2022) Status and perspectives of non-biogenic renewable gases. IEA Bioenergy TCP, Paris, France. https://www.ieabioenergy.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/IEA-Bioenergy-Renewable-Gas-Intertask-WP2-Synthesis-report_2022.pdf

states. However, we advocate that Ireland embraces the potential ‘latecomer advantage’⁸. Ireland has scope to adopt a hydrogen strategy which is much more realistic as regards the energy security rationale for a hydrogen transition, whereas other national strategies have been shaped by heavy industry or traditional energy sectors and their climate abatement needs. Given recent dramatic shocks to the European energy system, notably the dramatic disruption in natural gas supply and price stability associated with Russia’s invasion of Ukraine, **Ireland’s hydrogen strategy must be part of a renewed focus on national energy diversity and resilience**. This will require proactive management of demand across many sectors, a sustained engagement between national, EU and international commercial innovators, as well as the nurturing of a sufficiently large and resilient hydrogen research community on the island of Ireland.

We wholeheartedly welcome the opportunity to participate in the development of Ireland’s national hydrogen strategy. The remainder of submission consists of sections corresponding to those in the public consultation document, with the exception of the standalone section on *Energy Security*. We believe that energy security is as important as decarbonisation and should therefore be considered throughout our submission, not in isolation.

Research

As a leader in hydrogen research in Ireland, we welcome the prominent positioning of research within the consultation document. **Public funding for hydrogen research should be increased** at all stages including fundamental discovery, device design, first-of-a-kind deployment, socio-economic studies, and policy studies. The current level and timeframe of funding for hydrogen research in Ireland relies heavily on a model of precarious employment contracts for early-stage researchers. Due to employment insecurity, these researchers frequently leave Ireland to take up more positions elsewhere. This impedes the growth of Ireland’s hydrogen knowledge resource. Given the importance of hydrogen in Ireland’s decarbonisation and energy security, **we recommend the establishment of an interdisciplinary national hydrogen centre of excellence**, to better enable collaboration between researchers, industry, policymakers, and the public. Key research activities for the medium term include:

- Development of a **national hydrogen roadmap**, similar to one developed at the University of Galway for the West of Ireland shown in Figure 1, **to help determine a coherent direction for hydrogen deployment in Ireland**. Such a national roadmap would recognise challenges, develop paths forward, and maximise synergies in hydrogen supply and demand.
- Nurture Ireland’s islands as sites for hydrogen innovation. Valentia Island, the Aran Islands, Achill Island, Arranmore, and Rathlin Island have published or are publishing [hydrogen feasibility studies](#) as part of their local decarbonisation plans. This trend is apparent across Europe too.
- Model the role of expedited deployment of hydrogen in Ireland’s energy transition. An example of this type of modelling is this recent work by MaREI researchers⁹.
- Develop strategies for the optimisation of economically and environmentally sustainable hydrogen supply chains and their clustering into hydrogen valleys, building on work currently

⁸ Perkins, Richard, and Eric Neumayer. "The international diffusion of new technologies: A multitechnology analysis of latecomer advantage and global economic integration." *Annals of the association of American Geographers* 95(4) (2005): 789-808.

⁹ <https://www.marei.ie/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Our-Climate-Neutral-Future-Zero-by-50-Skillnet-Report-March-2021-Final-2.pdf>

underway at the University of Galway^{10,11}. Expand this work to include supply chains for sustainable sources of CO₂, to produce zero emissions renewable drop-in hydrocarbon fuels like e-methanol or e-kerosene.

- Strengthen the scientific and technological research on hydrogen technologies, from innovative hydrogen production devices, hydrogen storage materials, fuel cells and hydrogen utilisation combined with CO₂ or nitrogen-containing molecules^{12,13}.
- Explore the potential for geological storage of hydrogen across the island of Ireland and offshore.

Demand

Hydrogen can play important roles in the decarbonisation and strengthening of energy security and resilience in several demand sectors. Energy efficiency improvements, electrification and biofuels have important roles in some of these sectors. It is important that end users be encouraged to pursue the decarbonisation options most sustainable and suitable to their needs, bearing in mind sectoral emissions reduction targets. We present our own version of the “hydrogen ladder” in Figure 2 to illustrate where we believe hydrogen could be directed in Ireland’s energy transition. We urge caution in the use of tools such as “hydrogen ladders” as they can convey an overly simplistic, deterministic view of a very complex and uncertain challenge in which technology and local conditions constantly evolve. For example, electrification of taxi fleets may be preferable to hydrogen, but to what extent are grid capacity issues and their impact on charging considered? We recognise, however, that such graphical tools are useful in starting conversations on decarbonisation. We have also added a block of potential new hydrogen demands that encompasses exports of ammonia, production (and export) of fertiliser based on ammonia, production (and export) of methanol and e-fuels (e-kerosene and shipping fuels), use of hydrogen to refine alumina to aluminium, use of alumina “red mud” by-product to produce and export iron, and the attraction of energy-intensive FDI to Ireland due to availability of secure, resilient zero carbon electricity and hydrogen. The proposed ladder attempts to be Ireland-specific and reflect the realities of the development and deployment of zero carbon technologies.

¹⁰ Tubagus Aryandi Gunawan and Ian Williamson and Diana Raine and Rory F.D. Monaghan (2021) 'Decarbonising city bus networks in Ireland with renewable hydrogen'. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 46 :28870-28886. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.11.164>

¹¹ Tubagus Aryandi Gunawan and Rory F.D. Monaghan (2022) 'Techno-econo-environmental comparisons of zero- and low-emission heavy-duty trucks'. *Applied Energy*, 308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.118327>

¹² Sean Hennessey and Pau Farràs (2018) 'Production of solar chemicals: gaining selectivity with hybrid molecule/semiconductor assemblies'. *Chemical Communication*, 54: 6662-6680. <https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2018/cc/c8cc02487a/>

¹³ Paolo Dessì and Laura Rovira-Alsina and Carlos Sánchez and G. Kumaravel Dinesh and Wenming Tong and Pritha Chatterjee and Michele Tedesco and Pau Farràs and Hubertus M.V. Hamelers and Sebastià Puig (2021) 'Microbial electrosynthesis: Towards sustainable biorefineries for production of green chemicals from CO₂ emissions'. *Biotechnology Advances*, 46, 107675. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0734975020301774>

Phase 1 and 2 funding could qualify for Climate Action Fund Support. All of these proposals involve commercial bodies which can be expected to contribute to the costs.

Figure 1: Hydrogen roadmap developed for the West of Ireland as part of the SEAFUEL project

Figure 2: Hydrogen ladder for Ireland proposed by the University of Galway

To get an understanding of the potential future demands of hydrogen, we present the figure below. This simply takes the current energy demands in some of the sectors identified in the hydrogen ladder and assumes that 25% (low), 50% (medium) and 75% (high) of that energy demand is instead met by hydrogen. The fuels displaced by hydrogen in these scenarios are natural gas, kerosene, LPG, diesel, marine diesel, and heavy fuel oil. This does not account for the future trajectory of sectoral demand, which is beyond the scope of this submission, but sets broadly understood boundaries on potential domestic hydrogen demand. This simplified analysis does not include the use of hydrogen for long-term energy storage as the future size of this requirement is difficult to assess. Total hydrogen demands in the three scenarios range from 9 TWh to 28 TWh. The 2021 CAP referenced 1-3 TWh of renewable gas by 2030. Assuming that in each scenario, hydrogen is produced by electrolyzers with 70% efficiency and 85% capacity factor, the low, medium, and high scenarios require 1.7 GW, 3.4 GW, and 5.1 GW of installed electrolyser capacity, respectively. These figures should be compared to the 12-13 GW of intended wind energy capacity by 2030, the 50-75 GW of offshore wind capacity in Ireland's EEZ, and 2 GW electrolyser target recently announced by Government. **We believe the low demand scenario, with 2 GW of electrolyzers, is plausible by 2030, and the medium, with 4 GW, by the mid-2030s.**

Figure 3: Estimates for low, medium, and high hydrogen demand scenarios in key sectors

Hydrogen Valleys are regional clusters of producers and users, which are intended to drive down costs through economies of scale and de-risk projects. The EU's Clean Hydrogen Partnership is targeting funding at Hydrogen Valleys due to their ability to serve as first movers for hydrogen. The [Galway Hydrogen Hub](#) (GH2) aims to be Ireland's first Hydrogen Valley by clustering potential regional hydrogen users in the public transport, haulage, fleet vehicle, ferry, and construction material sectors into a single multi-modal hydrogen. The source of electricity for the electrolyser will be renewable electricity. Hydrogen Valleys enable synergies including larger-scale, more cost-effective storage, the ability to have different hydrogen demand patterns from different users "smooth out" overall demand, a new route to market for renewable resources for which electrical grid connections are impractical. Taken together, **Hydrogen Valleys can play a role alongside energy efficiency and electrification in full energy system decarbonisation.**

The Green Hysland project, in which University of Galway researchers work, is arguably the most relevant Hydrogen Valley for Ireland, given the similarities between Ireland and Mallorca, which include island energy systems, abundant variable renewables, relatively low energy intensity of industry, and the importance of a pristine environment for tourism.

Decarbonisation targets for energy end use sectors have been set. **Sustainability criteria should be imposed on both electricity and hydrogen and the end user should be left to determine the best route to decarbonise their energy/fuel use.** This could be electrification in many cases and hydrogen in others. Avoiding increasing energy use (through hydrogen use) is an arbitrary objective. Avoiding *unnecessary* energy use is important, but such a goal should not stand in the way of overall deeper decarbonisation, more energy security, improved routes to market and term storage for renewables, which could ultimately lead to more cost-effective decarbonisation.

Supply

Direct connections to onshore and offshore wind farms and solar farms appear to be the most obvious ways to power hydrogen supply, but there are other options. Wind farms with grid connections and electrolyser would have two routes to market and the ability to export electricity at a more constant rate. As the overall electricity grid decarbonises, grid powered electrolysers will be more capable of producing low-carbon hydrogen. This is already possible at certain times of day. Curtailment is also a potentially useful source of electricity, but given the infrequency of curtailment, its use *at scale* could lead to low electrolyser capacity factors, and difficult business cases. Proposals for approaches to de-risk hydrogen production are to:

1. **Mandate low-carbon hydrogen production targets**, for example using power purchase agreements. The low-carbon credentials of the hydrogen must be measurable by a scheme such as [CertifHy](#).
2. **Create stable, reliable demand for hydrogen in hard-to-abate sectors** by:
 - a. Fully implementing the EU's Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Requirement for regular gaseous and liquid hydrogen filling along the TEN-T network,
 - b. Building out and expanding the planned NI-ROI East and West coast hydrogen corridors,
 - c. Incentivising gas-fired turbine/engine operators to introduce hydrogen to their fuel mix and gradually increase the content.
 - d. Expanding supports for zero emissions heavy duty vehicles
3. **Provide green hydrogen price support through instruments like contracts for difference (CfDs) or similar,**
4. **Have clearly defined positions on safety and certifications,**
5. **Speed the planning process for all energy and transportation infrastructure.**

Competition between hydrogen and direct electrification in the sectors we have identified is not necessarily a problem. The goal for end users, which should be encouraged government policy, is decarbonisation. An additional goal for national policy is energy security. The end users in the identified sectors will deploy the most suitable technology or practice for their sector. In many cases, that will be electrification, and in others that will be hydrogen. It should not be the role of government departments to make these technical and business decisions for the end users.

For deployment at scale, **the best location for hydrogen production is near its use site**. Ports are an obvious choice for deployment. They are near offshore renewables, see large volumes of HGV traffic, many of them have green/brown field sites available, and they present export opportunities. Other options include transportation hub and distribution centres, and large industry sites including data centres. Deployment of hydrogen production at its use site instead of the site of availability of renewables requires guarantees of origin (GoOs) for the electricity and in turn for the hydrogen. The most widely used GoO system for hydrogen is CertifHy. Only hydrogen that meets strict sustainability criteria should be supported by CfDs.

In the current era of focus on energy security, subsidising the price of imported fossil fuels to all but those in most need is counterproductive. Instead of subsidising imported fossil fuels, which does nothing for energy security or decarbonisation, these funds should be used to subsidise domestically produced renewable electricity and hydrogen. **If fully deployed in the sectors indicated above, fossil fuels could be almost completely phased out by hydrogen use.** If hydrogen were to be mandated to be blended with fuels in on-site power generation, for example at data centres, factories, etc, peak

grid electricity demand could be reduced, alongside decarbonisation and import offsetting. Ireland has several key strengths in becoming a producer of hydrogen:

1. An extremely large renewable energy production capability, only fully exploitable via linking to long-term storage such as hydrogen.
2. Proximity to major existing hydrogen demand centres in Europe (Germany, Netherlands, Belgium) that are now mandated to decarbonise and will not be able to meet their own demands with domestic production.
3. A strong research base in academia with excellent links to industry.
4. Strong and decisive policy direction in the form of the CAP and the sectoral emissions reduction targets.

Transportation and Storage

Transportation

Given its nature, most Hydrogen Valley projects, with the obvious exception of export projects, seek to reduce the transport of hydrogen as much as possible. If transport is unavoidable, high-pressure (350-500 bar) tube trailers appear to be the most suitable near term means in Ireland today. **There is interest in blending hydrogen into the gas grid for delivery to end users, but we are uncertain of the merits** of this for the following reasons:

- Blending hydrogen with natural gas means it can only be used for heating or power generation, not for higher value uses in transportation or chemicals production.
- Power generation is a higher value use than heat. All gas power plants are supplied by the high-pressure, steel transmission system (Tx), which is not suited to high blend rates of hydrogen.
- The distribution system (Dx), on the other hand, is low-pressure and made of polyethylene, which can accommodate much higher hydrogen percentages. But the Dx primarily supplies domestic, commercial, and industrial gas users.
- Domestic gas use is likely to be primarily decarbonised by electrification via heat pumps. This will likely be similar for commercial users, whose premises are small and whose gas use is focused on space and water heating, which can be electrified.
- This leaves industrial gas users on the Dx as the final recipient of hydrogen blended in the gas grid. We are uncertain of the costs and benefits of modifying the existing gas grid to deliver hydrogen to this subset of end users.

If on-site production is not an option, a better way of transporting hydrogen to power generators on the Tx and industrial users on the Dx could be to build new pipelines (not networks as such) to bring 100% hydrogen from production site to demand location. These pipelines would not be as comprehensive as the existing gas network as they would only be serving those customers that cannot be decarbonised by other means. This strategy would align with the [European Hydrogen Backbone Initiative](#) (EHB), which seeks to develop infrastructure to transport 100% hydrogen by pipe. One part of the Irish gas grid that is currently omitted from the EHB is the pipeline that connects the Corrib gas field to the Tx near Galway. The Corrib gas terminal is in one of the richest resources of onshore and offshore wind energy in western Europe. Green hydrogen injected into the pipeline could be used to transport this to demand centres in Galway and onwards to Dublin, Limerick, and Cork. **As production from the Corrib field declines over the next decade, studies on the feasibility of converting/replacing the Tx pipeline to 100% hydrogen should be explored.**

Storage

Hydrogen storage is crucial for Ireland. Without large-scale, cheap storage, green hydrogen, which is produced at variable rates by renewable energy, will be very expensive to be delivered at rates required by end users. **The salt cavern storage site being developed at Islandmagee, County Antrim, is vital for the development of hydrogen on the island of Ireland.** Research should also be undertaken into the prospects for hydrogen storage in the Corrib field or other geological structures around Ireland. Non-geological storage will need to be developed also. This will need to consider the forms that hydrogen may be exported from Ireland. For example, to simply supply the Irish demand, high-pressure storage may suffice. If, however, export is an important driver of hydrogen production, the means of that hydrogen export (liquefied, ammonia, methanol, etc) will impact on domestic decisions. Ports again have important role to play as production, storage, and distribution hubs, or Hydrogen Valleys. A major challenge associated with large-scale hydrogen storage is ensuring the energy security policy in place allows for a viable business case. Ireland used to store natural gas in the depleted Kinsale gas field, but that ceased, and the facility has now been dismantled. Such a gas storage site would be extremely valuable now. **What lessons can be learned from that experience to ensure hydrogen storage has a future in Ireland?**

Export Opportunity

In a similar way to Hydrogen Valleys, export projects benefit from economies of scale and therefore drive lower unit production costs, and more importantly, storage costs, for both domestic and overseas customers. Export could and should play a vital role in developing Ireland's hydrogen supply. It will enable routes to market for offshore wind in locations where no local demand exists, and electrical grid construction would be impractical. Both hydrogen and electricity (HVDC) exports will benefit Ireland. These two routes to the European market have distinct advantages. HVDC is a more efficient way to transmit renewable energy, but the issue of storage is unaddressed. Hydrogen on the other hand is less efficient but can be stored at scale. Additionally, when exported by ship, it can be directed to the highest bidder in the same way that oil and LNG tankers can. This would enable Ireland to sell its renewable energy to a much wider market. Germany and the Netherlands have ambitious clean hydrogen use targets that would take a large portion of Ireland's potential hydrogen export capacity. Nevertheless, for this export potential to be realised, considerable foresight, planning and delivery will be required for state-of-the-art hydrogen port/shipping infrastructure. Thus, in the short term, there is a pressing need for Irish regulators to ensure that certification problems are resolved, and adequate European level mutual recognition is advanced. Ireland must take advantage of being inside the EU and also having strong interconnections with the British energy networks and regulatory authorities.

By 2030, we estimate that liquid hydrogen or ammonia (for ammonia end use) tankers will be viable. If sustainable cost-effective CO₂ can be sourced, the conversion of hydrogen to e-methanol or e-kerosene could be preferable, as they are easier to ship than liquid hydrogen or ammonia. A subsea pipeline capable of carrying 100% hydrogen for export to the UK by the mid-2030s, thus allowing greater two-way integration with the EHB, should be investigated.

Exports could be enabled by (1) streamlining the planning and consenting processes for large energy and other infrastructure projects, and (2) establishing something like a royalties payment for green hydrogen exported from Ireland. This would be similar to how fossil fuel exporters like Norway require the state to be paid for its natural resources.

Safety and Regulation

We are not experts in safety or regulation, but we do have expertise on public perception and support. As regards safety, regulation, and risk mitigation we draw attention to an important issue of the public communication of hydrogen science and risks. The Irish public's perception, reception and support for hydrogen will be crucial for a successful transition¹⁴. It should therefore be an important part of any national hydrogen strategy. We draw attention to the existing social science literature which has identified that new technologies, and hydrogen in particular, can easily fall victim to heightened risk perception and fear^{15,16,17}. We advocate a two-pronged focus here. First, there is a need for a **dedicated public communication campaign which in general can cleverly communicate the science and risk factors for hydrogen** and its underlying potential and importance. Secondly, we advise the development of a more **participatory community-based form for engagement with the potential for hydrogen development and infrastructure** that would overlap with identified sites of interest and potential.

Supports and Targets

The Need for a Hydrogen Policy Champion

For hydrogen to have long-term potential to grow, mature and offer the full range of their potential, a strong and unambiguous institutional champion is probably essential. Some social science literature has affirmed the importance of institutional policy champions in bringing about substantial change^{18,19}. It should be noted that for the electricity and gas sectors, there are very well established and effective institutional actors (EirGrid, ESB, Gas Networks Ireland, etc.) who play a vital role in advancing the merits, technical details, and special requirements for their particular area of expertise. There are also institutions such as the SEAI who are crucial in encouraging and steering the energy transition. However, there is no equivalent state or semi-state organisation or institution to provide sustained and dedicated leadership for hydrogen in Ireland from the perspective of public policy. There are of course many commercial actors interested in hydrogen, including some SME and research led starts ups which are part of an emergent hydrogen economy. Hydrogen Ireland represents the growing hydrogen industry on the island. There is also more general policy expertise and leadership capacity within the civil service focused on energy policy. However, what is arguably required is more

¹⁴ Gordon, Joel A., Nazmiye Balta-Ozkan, and Seyed Ali Nabavi. "Beyond the triangle of renewable energy acceptance: The five dimensions of domestic hydrogen acceptance." *Applied Energy* 324 (2022): 119715.

¹⁵ Stalker, Linda, Jennifer Roberts, Leslie Mabon, and Patrick Hartley. "Communicating leakage risk in the hydrogen economy: lessons already learned from geoenergy industries." *Frontiers Energy Research* (2022): In-press.

¹⁶ Glover, Katherine, Jennifer A. Rudd, Daniel R. Jones, Elaine Forde, Michael EA Warwick, William JF Gannon, and Charles W. Dunnill. "The hydrogen bike: communicating the production and safety of green hydrogen." *Frontiers in Communication* 5 (2021): 540635.

¹⁷ Huijts, Nicole MA. "The emotional dimensions of energy projects: Anger, fear, joy and pride about the first hydrogen fuel station in the Netherlands." *Energy research & social science* 44 (2018): 138-145.

¹⁸ Gore, Tony. (2014) "The role of policy champions and learning in implementing horizontal environmental policy integration: comparative insights from European Structural Fund Programmes in the UK." *Administrative Sciences* 4(3): 304-330.

¹⁹ Eames, Malcolm, and William McDowall. (2010) "Hydrogen transitions: a socio-technical scenarios approach." pp. 113-142. In *Hydrogen Energy*, in Ekins, Paul (ed.) *Hydrogen Energy: Economic and Social Challenges*. London: Earthscan/ Routledge,

sustained 'bridging leadership' on hydrogen which is directed to achieving wider public policy goals while exhibiting the required technical expertise which will be required for complex issues such as certification and cross border technical agreements on hydrogen exports, gas blends and imports/exports. We recommended that Ireland should actively consider establishing a small, bespoke, but expert and dedicated hydrogen energy agency or institution which can provide this type of technical policy leadership.

Other Measures

The government recently set a target of 2 GW of hydrogen production by 2030. We believe this is a plausible target and should be pursued. It should be followed by targets of 4 GW by the mid-2030s and 6-8 GW by the early 2040s. It is vital for the development of hydrogen in Ireland that the sectoral emissions caps in the CAP be adhered to. Taxes on imported fossil fuels and carbon emissions should also be increased, with revenue going towards those least able to pay higher energy costs and also to supporting renewable electricity and domestic hydrogen production through instruments like CfDs, and expanding the grant support scheme for zero emissions vehicles. GoOs for hydrogen should be permitted subject to sustainability criteria, such as CertifHy, being met. Support for both CAPEX and OPEX for hydrogen production projects should be provided. Operators of on-site gas-burning generators such as data centres and manufacturing sites should be incentivised to blend gradually increasing percentages of hydrogen in their fuel. Given the key role that Hydrogen Valleys are recognised to play across Europe, the national strategy should support those first movers in this space in Ireland, particularly in Galway, the Shannon Estuary and Cork Harbour.